

An Optimal Solution for Dynamic Polar Diagram

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Abstract

The Polar Diagram [1] of a set of points is a partition of the plane, a locus approach for problems processing angles. Also, Dynamic Polar Diagram is a problem in which some points can be added to or removed from the point set. Sadeghi et al. [4] introduced this problem and presented an algorithm which is optimal in the case that some points are deleted from the points set. But, that algorithm is not optimal when some new points are inserted into the diagram. Here, "Optimality" is to redraw only the regions that would be changed. We present two algorithms to solve this problem in optimal time in case of inserting new points into the diagram. Both algorithms run in $O(k)$ time in which $1 \leq k \leq n$ is the number of the sites which their regions would be changed.

1 Introduction

C. I. Grima et al. [1] introduced the concept of the Polar Diagram. This diagram is a plane partition with similar features to those of the Voroni diagram. In fact the Polar Diagram can be seen in the context of generalized Voronoi diagram. The polar angle of a point p with respect to a point s_i , denoted by $ang_{s_i}(p)$, is the angle formed by the positive horizontal line of p and the straight line linking p and s_i . Given a set S of n points in the plane, the locus of points with smaller positive polar angle with respect to $s_i \in S$ is called polar region of s_i and denoted by P_{s_i} . Thus,

$$P_{s_i} = \{(x, y) \in E^2 | ang_{s_i}(x, y) < ang_{s_j}(x, y); \forall j \neq i\}. \quad (1)$$

Each polar region, as observed in the Fig 1, is constructed using two different half-lines or polar edges. There is always a horizontal edge starting at each s_i , $\{(x, y), x < x_i\}$, and another oblique polar edges with the gradient of the straight line crossing s_i and s_k , with $s_i \in P_{s_k}$ that is called *model line*. in this case we call s_k the *parent* of s_i denoted by $s_k = Par(s_i)$

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Figure 1: The Polar Diagram of a set of points in plane. The polar region of each site is constructed by horizontal and model lines.

or $s_i \prec s_k$.

The plane is divided into different regions in such a way that if point $(x, y) \in E^2$ lies in P_{s_i} , it is known that s_i is the first site found performing an angular scanning starting from (x, y) . The boundary is the horizontal line crossing the top most site of S . Fig. 1 depicts the Polar Diagram of an exemplary set of points on the plane. Also for n points on the plane, it is not possible to compute the Polar Diagram in less than $\Theta(n \log n)$ time [1, 3].

There are at least two optimal approaches for the Polar Diagram construction, the Incremental and the Divide and Conquer methods, both working in optimal time. For computing the Polar Diagram using the Incremental method, suppose S is sorted from top to down obtaining the sequence s_0, s_1, \dots, s_{i-1} . The polar region of s_i is computed after $P_{s_0}, P_{s_1}, \dots, P_{s_{i-1}}$ are processed. Suppose s_i is in the region of s_j . The model line of P_{s_i} crosses s_i and s_j , and by drawing the horizontal half-line of s_i , the boundary of P_{s_i} will be introduced [3, 5, 6].

In this paper, we consider a general position condition which no three point sites could be located in a straight line. Section 2 consists the general information about dynamic polar diagram. In Section 3, we present some new definitions which we need in the next parts. In Section 4, we introduce our algorithms and Section 5 includes the conclusion.

2 Dynamic Polar Diagram

Sadeghi et al. [4] introduced a problem called Dynamic Polar Diagram. In this problem, some points can be added to, or removed from the point set. Solution to this problem is to redraw the Polar Diagram in the minimum time. Sadeghi et al. propose to determine an area out of which the Polar Diagram does not change due to the insertion or deletion on the new sites. Although, solving the deletion process was opti-

mum, there are several examples that show this algorithm would not solve the problem in optimum time when some new points are inserted into the point set. Solving the problem in case of insertion has remained an open problem [4]. We introduce two algorithms to find the actual changes in diagram when some new sites are inserted into the point set. We apply the algorithms to each site one by one, the same way as Sadeghi et al. did, so we can say our algorithms are an online solution to the Dynamic Polar Diagram problem.

3 Definitions and Preliminaries

Definition 1 *Complement Area for each polar region P_{s_i} is denoted by $Com(P_{s_i})$ and constructed using two half-lines or edges, one is the horizontal half-line $\{(x, y_i), x > x_i\}$ and the other is a half-line which links s_i to $Par(s_i)$ and extends up to the infinity (Fig 2)*

For each polar region P_{s_i} , $Com(P_{s_i})$ is bounded between two lines that we know their equations, so

$$\begin{aligned}
 Com(P_{s_i}) &= \{(x, y) | x > x_i, \\
 y_{s_i} < y < \frac{y_{Par(s_i)} - y_i}{x_{Par(s_i)} - x_i} (x - x_i) + y_i\} \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2 *Parallel Complement Area for each polar region P_{s_i} is a sub area of $Com(P_{s_i})$ which is above $P_{Par(s_i)}$ and is denoted by $PCom(P_{s_i})$.*

we can write the relations as follows,

$$\begin{aligned}
 Com(P_{s_i}) &= \{(x, y) | x > x_{Par(s_i)}, \\
 y_{Par(s_i)} < y < \frac{y_{Par(s_i)} - y_i}{x_{Par(s_i)} - x_i} (x - x_i) + y_i\} \quad (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 1 *The parallel complement area of each polar region P_{s_i} is a subset of complement area of P_{s_j} which $s_j = Par(s_i)$, denoted $PCom(P_{s_i}) \subset Com(P_{s_j})$.*

Proof. The proof is rather obvious. According to general position condition, s_i and s_j should not be on a straight line, so for each site s_i, s_j which $s_i \prec s_j$, the model line of region P_{s_i} forms a non-zero angle T with the model line of region P_{s_j} (Fig 2) and the region $PCom(P_{s_i})$ is always in $Com(P_{s_j})$. \square

We are going to find the polar regions which is be changed by inserting a new site s_k into the diagram. The position of the sites are fixed, so the horizontal edge of polar regions will remain unchanged. Also, changing of the model line of P_{s_i} leads to changing the shape of P_{s_i} .

The inserted point would effect the polar region P_{s_i} whether by changing its model line (changing the

Figure 2: The complement area and the parallel complement area of polar region P_{s_i} are shown on the right. The parallel complement area of each polar region P_{s_i} is a subset of complement area of $P_{Par(s_i)}$, which is shown on the left.

shape of the region), or by falling inside a region or intersecting a region (changing the boundaries of the region). when the regions boundaries are changed, the incremental method would draw the new regions without any change in the algorithm procedure. Suppose s_j is the first lower site from the site s_k which is located on the right site of its horizontal line specifies the boundaries of P_{s_k} . By redrawing P_{s_k}, \dots, P_{s_j} according to the incremental method, diagram update procedure would be complete. But the changes in the shape of regions should be studied in another way that will be discussed next.

We introduce a lemma that holds a necessary and sufficient condition for changing the shape of a polar region, when a new site is inserted into the diagram.

Lemma 2 *For any new site s_k in Polar Diagram, the shape of polar region P_{s_i} will be changed if and only if $s_k \in Com(P_{s_i})$.*

Proof. Let $s_j = Par(s_i)$, if $s_k \in Com(P_{s_j})$, then from (2), $y_{s_i} < y_{s_k}$. We can assume two cases, one in which $y_{s_i} < y_{s_k} \leq y_{s_j}$ and the other $y_{s_j} \leq y_{s_k}$, so:

1) In the case where $y_{s_i} < y_{s_k} \leq y_{s_j}$, new site s_k is located between horizontal lines crossing s_i and s_j . Whether the position of s_k is in p_{s_j} or not, s_k is either $s_k \in Com(P_{s_i}) \cap P_{s_j}$ or $s_k \notin Com(P_{s_i}) \cap P_{s_j}$, so:

a) If $s_k \notin Com(P_{s_i}) \cap P_{s_j}$, then the horizontal line of P_{s_k} will cut the whole of the polar region P_{s_j} , and s_i is not a child of s_j any longer, and there is no other sites between s_i and s_k so $s_i \prec s_k$.

b) If $y_{s_i} < y_{s_k} \leq y_{s_j}$ and $s_k \in P_{s_j}$, then s_k is located in a triangular cell (Fig 3) and the model line of P_{s_k} would be drawn to link s_j and s_k which intersects the base of triangular cell. Then, the polar region of s_k will include s_i and the model line of P_{s_k} would be changed.

2) In the second case, $y_{s_j} \leq y_{s_k}$, suppose sequence $s = s_i, s_{k-1}, s_k$ is a set of sites that includes s_i and s_k and is between them. Again let $s_j = Par(s_i)$; we show that s_k would be the new parent of s_i . From Lemma 1, $s_k \in PCom(P_{s_i}) \subset Com(P_{s_j})$. Without

Figure 3: The position of a new site s_k in the complement area of P_{s_i} .

Figure 4: The position of a new site s_k when it is not located in the complement area of P_{s_i} .

loss of generality consider s_k to be located between s_i and s_j . From case 1, s_k is the new parent of s_j , then the new model line of P_{s_j} changes in a way that the polar region P_{s_j} , no longer includes s_i (Fig 3). From the general position condition, $\theta_1 > 0$ (s_k and s_j are not on a direct line), this causes P_{s_j} not to include s_i any longer. However $\theta_2 > 0$ as well, where θ_2 is the angle made by the model lines of P_{s_j} and P_{s_k} , and this makes that new polar region P_{s_k} to cover all of the missing points of old P_{s_j} , so s_i will be in P_{s_k} and P_{s_i} would be changed. We claim that our assumption does not interfere with the generality of the problem, because if s_j be the indirect parent of s_i , $s_i < s_{i+1} < \dots < s_j$, then with the same method and making two angles $\theta_1, \theta_2 > 0$, for each pair of these sites, eventually, we conclude s_k is the new parent of s_i .

On the other hand, we are going to prove if the shape of a polar region P_{s_i} would change by inserting a new site s_k , s_k is located in $Com(P_{s_i})$. Suppose this, is not true (proof by contradiction) and s_k is the new parent of s_i which is not located in $Com(P_{s_i})$. In this case, s_k must be located in $C = Plane - Com(P_{s_i})$ which is shown in Fig 4. If s_k is below s_i , there is a contradiction, because it can not be a parent of s_i and below s_i . Else if, s_k is located above s_i , it would be either in a polar region of s_j which $s_j = Par(s_i)$, or in P_{s_j} which s_j is not located in $Com(s_i)$ (if s_j be located in $Com(s_i)$) then from case 1, it should be the parent of s_i . On one hand s_k is located in polar region of parent s_i and it is obvious that P_{s_k} will not include s_i (Fig 4), on the other hand, if s_k is located in the other region, It would not cut the region of s_j and change the model line of P_{s_i} , so there is a contradiction. \square

Figure 5: The Polar Diagram with 3 sites which the CPD is drawn on it, the colored regions are SI_i and the rest make the Null regions (left). Corresponding tree with new site s_k (right).

Lemma 2 is a necessity for finding the changing regions when a site is inserted into the diagram.

We introduce two algorithms which one of them explore the diagram using some preprocesses, but the other find the changing regions simultaneously. Each one has its own advantages that we will discuss later.

We need a tree that corresponds to the diagram. Each node v_i of the tree corresponds to a site s_i of the diagram. If s_j be the parent of s_i , then there is an edge $v_i v_j$ in the tree that could model the parent to child relations. With the help of searching algorithms, the tree would be useful to seek the changing regions.

Definition 3 For each site s_i , Symmetry Indexing Region of s_i , denoted by SI_i , is a sub area of $Com(P_{s_i})$ which is not in $PCom(P_{s_i})$, $SI_i = Com(P_{s_i}) - PCom(P_{s_i})$ (Fig 5).

Definition 4 We name the area which is not in any SI_i , the Null region of the diagram (Fig 5).

We use these definitions to produce a new diagram which is used in our algorithm.

Definition 5 Complementary diagram for Polar Diagram, denoted by CPD , is a partition of the plane which is constructed by two regions, The Null region and the SI region, $SI = \bigcup_i SI_i$ (Fig 5).

4 Algorithms

First algorithm functions by finding the starting point for exploring the diagram. When the new site s_k is inserted into the Polar Diagram, it would be located in one of the regions of the CPD , either in Null or in SI regions. It is obvious that, if s_k is located in the Null region, there would not be any changes in the shape of the regions (because Null region has no conjunction with the $Com(s_i)$ for all sites s_i). But if $s_k \in SI_i$, from Lemma 1, P_{s_i} is the first place where the diagram would be changed. The algorithm finds other changing regions by exploring the diagram using the corresponding tree.

From computational perspective, it is easy to find a SI_i where s_k is located in it, either using a standard point location algorithm or using the following two-step method:

1) From top to down, for each $s_i = (x_i, y_i)$, compare y_{s_i} and y_{s_k} , until $y_{s_k} < y_{s_i}$ is found. Then go to step 2.

2) If $y_k < \frac{y_{Par(s_i)} - y_i}{x_{Par(s_i)} - x_i}(x - x_i) + y_i$, s_k is located in SI_i , else s_k is located in Null region and does not make any changes in the shape of diagram.

Afterward, if $s_k \in SI_i$ we will continue the algorithm. We will find node v_i in the tree that corresponds to site s_i in the diagram and start exploration from its siblings, left to right. During exploration every site s_j will be checked by Lemma 2, if its region is changed or not. If a region is not changed, its children would not also change. The algorithm ignore them and continue the exploration for its siblings. Similarly, if a site s_i is not changed, its right hand's siblings will not also change. Because the sites with the same parent have bigger complement areas which cover the complement area of the P_{s_i} , the algorithm continues to find all of the changing regions.

Algorithm 1. inserting a new point to the Polar Diagram

Input: n sites on the plane, Polar Diagram, corresponding tree, CPD diagram and a new point site s_k .

Output: Polar Diagram of $n+1$ points

Step 1: Find SI_i from the CPD where s_k is located in.

Step 2: $s_k \rightarrow P$, $S' = \emptyset$

Step 3: Explore the tree from siblings of P , from left to right

3_1: if site s_i would change $s_i \rightarrow S'$ and $s_j \rightarrow P$ which s_j is one of the children of s_i goto Step 3

3_2: if site s_p does not change and if it is in the right side of s_i goto Step 4

Step 4: Update the diagram redrawing P_{s_i} , for all $s_i \in S'$

Here, we introduce another algorithm which does the whole exploration simultaneously. Firstly, we draw all the complement areas of regions. Secondly, for all sites s_i , we check if a new site s_k is in the $Com(P_{s_i})$ or not. Each polar region P_{s_j} with s_k in it, should be redrawn. So without changing the other regions, we would be able to update the diagram.

Algorithm 2. inserting a new point to the Polar Diagram

Input: set of n sorted sites S , Polar Diagram and new site s_k

Output: Polar Diagram of $n+1$ points

Step 1: $S' = \emptyset$

Step 2: for $s_i \in S$ draw the $Com(P_{s_i})$ and if $s_k \in Com(P_{s_i})$ then $s_i \rightarrow S'$

Step 3: update the diagram redrawing the P_{s_j} for $s_j \in S'$, by incremental method

Algorithms 1 and 2 are almost the same. They use a same method to find the changing regions, but their

searching models are different. Algorithm 1 does not need to save a lot of information and reach the required data by exploring the diagram step by step. But Algorithm 2 prepare all of the requirements at the beginning, then find all of the changing regions all together. Both of these algorithms have the same worst case and solve the problem in $O(k)$ time in which $1 \leq k \leq n$ is the number of the sites which their regions would be changed. Clearly this is Optimal in all cases. but each of them can perform better in special cases. If the new site s_k is located in the upper regions of the diagram, Algorithm 2 is recommended, because we need more exploration in the diagram and Algorithm 1 is not very useful. The more lower the location of the new site, the less exploration in the diagram is needed, and the first algorithm performs more better. Similarly the more the location of the new site s_k is to the left of the diagram, the more useful Algorithm 1 would become, because the prospects of s_k located in the Null region of CPD are more and Algorithm 1 would reach the answer sooner.

5 Conclusion

The Polar Diagram has been recently introduced by Grima et al. [1]. The dynamic version of this problem has also been discussed by Sadeghi et al. [4]. They introduced this problem and solved it using an algorithm which is optimal in the case that some points are deleted from the point set. But that algorithm is not optimal when some new points are inserted into the diagram.

In this paper, we presented two algorithms, both to solve the insertion case of Dynamic Polar Diagram in optimal time.

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